

The Impact of Green Marketing Strategies on the Brand Image of an Oil Distribution Company in Iraq

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 29 August 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Ghaith Hasan Kamil</p>	<p>This study examined the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq. The study used a descriptive analytical approach and a questionnaire to collect the necessary information. The study sample included 390 employees of an Iraqi oil products distribution company, who were selected using a random sampling method. The data were analyzed using the SPSS 25 statistical program.</p> <p>The statistical results showed that: Green marketing strategies impact the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq. There are significant differences in the average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq depending on years of practical experience among the study sample. The researcher recommended that petroleum product distribution companies adopt modern communication methods and use the internet as a cost-effective, environmentally friendly marketing strategy. These methods eliminate the need for paper, brochures, flyers, and booklets to promote and advertise environmentally friendly products, services, and initiatives, helping companies gain public approval.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Green marketing _ mental image _ brand _ petroleum products.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Green marketing is a social marketing strategy that addresses environmental and economic issues such as limited natural resources, environmental damage caused by traditional marketing, and the need to integrate environmentally friendly practices into marketing strategies. In the 1990s, marketing and economic research began focusing on "green advertising," which uses environmentally friendly phrases in advertisements to persuade consumers to make eco-friendly purchases (Al-Sharbiny, 2025, p. 162). Some consumers view this concept as related to environmental protection or the organization's social responsibility in production and marketing. In reality, however, the issue extends beyond that. Green marketing aims to positively impact customer preferences by encouraging them to seek environmentally friendly products and modify their purchasing and consumption habits accordingly. It also aims to provide an integrated marketing mix (Shaqlouf et al., 2024, p. 282). Some companies adopt green marketing strategies partly to change their brand image and link it to sustainable, contemporary strategies. A brand's image is essentially how consumers connect with and feel

attached to a brand. Brand image encompasses how the brand appears and how its use is perceived. In other words, brand image and awareness form the foundation of a brand's value. A positive brand image can be created by strengthening the relationship between the brand and consumers' memories of its marketing campaigns. Therefore, brand awareness and understanding must be established before consumers can respond positively to a campaign. If consumers are familiar with a brand, the company can spend less on brand extension and achieve higher sales (Khantar & Qalsh, 2019, p. 11).

1. Research Problem and Questions:

Today, Iraqi companies in various fields face major challenges in competitive local and global markets. Focusing solely on profits is no longer sufficient for measuring a company's success. Instead, attention has shifted to improving brand image among customers. This can be achieved by implementing strategies within the company's field of work that help create a positive brand image and ensure customer loyalty while attracting new customers. This requires Iraqi companies to adopt sustainable policies in production, distribution, and marketing, which is extremely important at present. Relying on green marketing strategies enhances a company's position and brand because green marketing

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principles are associated with environmental conservation and efforts to protect the environment by reducing emissions and improving the relationship between customers and products. This study aims to verify the impact of green marketing on the brand image of oil companies and how they supply products safely and sustainably. However, the tendency of Iraqi companies, including the Oil Products Distribution Company, to adopt green marketing strategies remains limited. Due to the slow adoption of this trend and the lack of awareness of its importance, the researcher poses the following question:

To what extent do green marketing strategies affect the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq?

2. Significance of the Study:

The study's importance stems from the following points:

- Highlighting green marketing as one of the most important and influential modern concepts and trends in marketing worldwide.

- Showing how much companies care about the environment as a significant source of competitive advantage by improving their brand image.

Applying the study to an oil products distribution company in Iraq demonstrates the extent to which oil companies care about improving their image and respecting the environment by reducing pollution through green marketing strategies.

This study contributes to the expansion of literature on green marketing, emphasizing the strategic value of brand image in promoting long-term sustainability in corporate operations.

3. Study Objectives:

- To determine the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq.

- To identify significant differences in the average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq, according to years of practical experience among the research sample.

4. Study Hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Green marketing strategies significantly impact the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq.

Hypothesis 2: There are no significant differences in average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq, based on years of practical experience among the research sample.

5. Study Limits and Methodology:

This section includes an explanation of the study population and sample, its limitations, methodology, and hypothetical outline.

5.1 Study Limits:

- Spatial limits: An oil products distribution company in Iraq.

- Temporal limits: The years 2024 and 2025.
- Human Limits: A group of employees at an oil products distribution company in Iraq.
- Objective limits: Study the impact of green marketing strategies on brand image.

5.2 Study Methodology:

The study relies on a descriptive-analytical approach as its general research methodology. The researcher proceeded with deduction as the primary method of reasoning because both the descriptive and analytical approaches align with the study's objectives and context. The researcher reviewed scientific studies and research addressing the impact of green marketing strategies on brand image. A questionnaire was used to conduct the fieldwork and was distributed to a purposive sample. The responses were analyzed using the SPSS 25 statistical analysis program.

5.3 Hypothetical Outline of the Study

Independent Variable: Green Marketing Strategies

Dependent Variable: Brand Image

Figure No. (1) Hypothetical plan of the study.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. The Origins of Green Marketing:

Green marketing emerged in the early 1970s when environmental issues began to receive widespread attention. The environmental movement forced companies to reconsider their actions and consider their environmental impact. The term "green marketing" was formally coined in the late 1980s and quickly gained popularity as a marketing tactic. In its early stages, green marketing focused on eco-labeling and emphasizing the environmental benefits of products. In addition to promoting energy-efficient appliances and recyclable materials, some leading companies began promoting eco-friendly products and messages in response to growing consumer awareness. Companies also began offering products with less packaging. However, green marketing has been met with skepticism due to concerns about "eco-misinformation," whereby companies exaggerate or make false claims about the environmental benefits of their products to attract environmentally conscious customers. The "green marketing" strategy employed by companies aims to produce and promote environmentally friendly and sustainable goods and services with minimal or no negative environmental impact (Deshmukh & Tare, 2024, p. 2).

22, P: 2).

2. The Concept of Green Marketing:

Green marketing is a broad concept that can be applied to all types of goods and services. It encompasses activities such

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as modifying products, altering manufacturing processes, changing packaging methods, revising promotional methods and pricing policies, and creating new distribution channels (Al-Sukari, 2023, p. 2). Green marketing aims to reduce painful environmental consequences by designing and producing environmentally friendly products and services. Green marketing encompasses many ideas, including creating and facilitating value that meets consumers' desires and needs. It involves maintaining and developing long-term relationships with partners, such as the environment, culture, and customers (Tan et al., 2022, p. 2).

3. The Importance of Green Marketing and Its Mechanisms

The green marketing mix refers to the environmentally friendly marketing of products. These strategies consider environmental protection from product development and promotion to distribution. Marketers follow environmentally safe strategies and adopt operational methods to improve product quality and packaging in an environmentally friendly manner. Consequently, green marketing has become an important component of many companies. Companies apply the green marketing mix to meet customers' current needs for safe, environmentally friendly products (Ahmed et al., 2023, p. 11477). To successfully adopt a green marketing philosophy, an organization must take steps to facilitate the process, including the following: (Morsi et al., 2025, p. 9). Expand the study of the organization's current environmental issues. Developing systems to measure and monitor environmental impacts resulting from organizational performance. Following up on the development of green marketing programs in light of emerging laws and regulations. Adopting appropriate methods to train and qualify employees in light of the organization's environmental orientation. Support environmental programs and efforts at various levels. Prepare scientific research to address environmental problems and the technologies used. Update educational programs to educate consumers and increase their awareness of environmental responsibility. Adopting appropriate methods to qualify business owners, producers, and others capable of steering their organizations in accordance with the government's desired environmental direction. Contributing to and establishing social organizations concerned with environmental and community issues.

4. Elements of Green Marketing

The elements of green marketing do not differ in their components from those of traditional marketing. However, the difference lies in the way these elements are formulated and managed to achieve the desired objectives. Green marketing seeks to achieve environmental and social objectives in addition to the traditional objectives of satisfying consumer desires and achieving the organization's profitability. Below, we review the most important elements

of the marketing mix for this concept: (Al-Sukari, 2023, p. 3), (Tamer, 2021, p. 172), (Yousefi and Youb, 2020, p. 93)

A. Green product: Any product designed or manufactured according to a set of standards aimed at protecting the environment and reducing the depletion of natural resources while maintaining its performance characteristics. Before embarking on the process of producing a green product, it is necessary to identify the environmental needs of the consumer and develop products according to these needs. A green product does not necessarily have to be entirely new; a set of modifications can be made to the existing product to make it environmentally friendly. These modifications include packaging methods, changing the proportions of some components, reusing some materials through recycling, or replacing other components with less environmentally impactful ones that do not produce environmentally harmful waste.

2. Green pricing: Pricing products to suit green consumers. However, these prices may include some additional costs due to the cost of ongoing research and development to ensure the use of environmentally friendly materials and new energy sources. The value of a product is usually represented by its performance, functionality, and other factors. Thus, the value of a product can be improved by adding an environmental character to it. Sometimes, companies reduce the prices of environmentally friendly products to encourage consumers to purchase them, as lowering prices is considered a more successful strategy for the company, and the environmental benefit can be used as a competitive advantage to justify the product price in the event of a change in the product's price. Its height.

3. Green Promotion: This includes all promotional activities within the environmental orientation, with a focus on guiding customers through environmental labels and information on the safe use of green products. It is a social interaction process aimed at eliminating the isolation that can occur between the organization, its audience, and its stakeholders. In other words, it includes all promotional activities within the environmental orientation.

5. The Concept of Brand Image

A brand's image is important. By telling the brand's story, one must understand its origin or creator, its narrative, its geography, and its advertising myth. All of these elements tell the brand's story. Therefore, we notice that many brands' history is shaped by a hero. This hero can be the brand's creator or a real person. This person contributes to making the dialogue between the brand and its customers credible, as well as its story. Therefore, the role of narrative allows the audience to connect with the brand and represents the starting point for forming a relationship between the brand and the consumer's image, which must be preserved. This narrative is developed through advertising, and through it, the brand is distinguished and established as a reference (Awfi, 2016, p. 10). It is also the cognitive construct of consumers that explains how a brand influences sales of a particular product

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or brand. Therefore, brand image is consumers' beliefs about a particular country's products, formed as a result of their cognitive awareness and accumulated experiences regarding the brand's strengths and weaknesses (Islam, Hussain, 2022).

Brand image is considered one of the crucial factors influencing consumer decisions. This image represents a set of beliefs, impressions, and ideas that consumers hold about a particular brand (Younis, 2024, p. 99).

Brand image is one of the primary factors that determine how consumers view a brand and the extent to which it influences their purchasing decisions. It is the overall impression formed in the public's mind based on their experiences, interactions, and the information they receive about the brand. This image is influenced by many factors, such as the quality of the product or service, advertising messages, and communication with customers, as well as the brand's reputation in the market (Shaarawy, 2025, p. 292).

A brand's mental image is the end result of the subjective impressions that individuals form regarding a particular individual or system. These impressions may be formed through direct or indirect experiences. These experiences are linked to individuals' emotions, attitudes, and beliefs, regardless of the accuracy of the information contained in the summary of these experiences. Ultimately, they represent a genuine motivation for their owners, through which they view and understand their surroundings (Nayli and Lamouchi, 2020, p. 399).

6. The Importance of Brand Image:

A brand's image creates value by allowing customers to process information more easily because it summarizes a set of characteristics. A brand's image also influences business performance and helps customers remember important details, such as the logo, when making a purchase. A brand's image provides reasons for purchase. These reasons lend credibility to the purchase, making it seem essential and legitimate and instilling confidence in customers. This relates to the brand's imaginative potential, which is based on objective and subjective elements. A positive brand image can also develop a positive sense of the brand and enhance and develop the personalities associated with the brand's communication or symbols (Sharf et al., 2020, p. 421).

Essentially, customers do not purchase the product itself, but rather the image associated with it and the value and benefits they perceive and obtain (Abu Al-Dahab et al., 2024, p. 199).

7. Characteristics of Brand Image:

A brand's image is characterized by the following features: (Rafida, 2025, p. 41).

A. Realism: A brand's image is realistic because it is a mental collection of the brand's characteristics based on consumers' personalities, inclinations, interests, and perceptions of the information they receive about the brand.

B. Generality: A brand's image is general because consumers primarily use it to evaluate a particular brand

based on their perception of the information they obtain and the influences they are exposed to.

C. Holistic nature: Like other human phenomena, this phenomenon is characterized by its universality, meaning a group of individuals share the same perception of a brand's image.

D. Subjectivity: The latter is characterized by a lack of objectivity because it relies on an individual's mindset, personality, and subjective aspects to shape it. These generalizations are based on opinions and impressions rather than empirical scientific evidence and are linked to subjective feelings and emotions.

8. The Impact of Green Marketing Strategies on Brand Image

Green branding is enhanced by aligning its identity with environmental principles and by focusing on environmental management, ethical behavior, and social responsibility. Companies also build credibility and the trust of consumers seeking sustainable options, creating a better brand image. Methods such as highlighting environmentally friendly materials and carbon-neutral practices contribute to establishing brands as sustainability leaders, helping them stand out in a competitive market (Al-Hamid, 2024, p. 38).

The results of numerous studies have also shown that green branding enhances consumer satisfaction with its products by ensuring that consumers' values are consistently reflected in their interactions with the brand, fostering lasting loyalty and strong, positive brand bonds (Huo, 2022).

▪ Green Marketing Strategies That Shape Brand Image

There are a set of strategies that green marketing relies on to shape brand image, including: (Abdeldaem and Boulgroun, 2020, p. 156)

A. Eliminating or Reducing the Concept of Waste: The focus has shifted to designing and producing products that are waste-free or recyclable, meaning that consideration has been given to how to reduce or eliminate waste.

B. Reshaping the Product Concept: This involves aligning production technology with the concept of environmental commitment, such that production relies heavily on environmentally friendly raw materials and minimal consumption. Furthermore, the products themselves must be recycled after the consumer has finished using them, especially durable ones, so that they can eventually be returned to their factory where they can be disassembled and recycled. Packaging, on the other hand, relies on environmentally friendly and recyclable raw materials.

C. Clarity of the relationship between price and cost: The price must reflect the actual cost of the product, or be close to it. Therefore, it must be commensurate with the true value of the product offered to customers (green product prices reflect not only the fact that the products do not harm the environment, but also the search for and preservation of alternative raw materials, which entail high costs, perhaps the

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most prominent of which is the cost of research and development).

▪ Factors Influencing Green Marketing Strategies That Shape the Brand Image

The most important elements influencing green marketing strategies that shape the brand image are four: (Shalaby and Shalaby, 2023, p. 797)

A. Word of mouth: This is oral communication between two people, through which the recipient understands information about the brand of the product or service in a way that is not commercial advertising. It is one of the most influential methods for convincing others to purchase the product or service and creating a favorable mental image of the product or service offered.

B. Organizational reputation: It can be said that an organization's reputation is a powerful asset that the organization benefits from in building brand loyalty. It is a source of expanding demand for the organization's products and maintaining the attractiveness of those products. A brand with a good reputation should have as its overriding goal the enhancement of its brand image. Brand reputation plays a significant role in consumer attachment and influence.

C. Customer Service and Brand Image: Customer service is defined as a set of intangible, value-driven activities that result in benefits that meet or exceed customer expectations and needs.

D. Advertising: This is a powerful means of garnering support for a specific idea or goal. Advertising has multiple means, including the media, talks, discussions, organizing seminars and conferences, and publishing books, among other methods.

III. FIELD STUDY

This section includes a description of the study methodology, population, and sample; the selection method; and the tools used. Data were collected through the distribution of questionnaires and then analyzed using appropriate statistical methods.

Study Population and Sample: The study population included all employees of the Oil Products Distribution Company in Iraq. The sample was intentional and comprised 390 employees who had practical experience, scientific knowledge, and familiarity with the research topic.

1. Sample Personal Data:

The sample is distributed according to their years of experience as follows:

- (36.2%) Less than 5 years.
- (39.5%) Between 5 and 10 years.
- (16.2%) Between 11 and 15 years.
- (8.2%) 16 years and older.

2. Criterion reliability and validity test (study tool):

Table (1): Cronbach's Alpha Values

Dimensions	Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)
Green Marketing Strategies	0.951
Brand Image	0.962
Overall Level of Investment	0.977

Source: SPSS v.25

The reliability coefficient value for all axes is greater than 0.70, so these values are statistically acceptable. This is because the values are significant when greater than 0.70, meaning distributing them to a group of individuals with the same characteristics will produce similar results.

3. Constructive validity:

Table (2): Correlation Coefficients

Dimensions	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Green Marketing Strategies	0.987	0.000
Brand Image	0.984	0.000

Source: SPSS v.25

We note that the Pearson coefficients are statistically significant, so the questionnaire is valid.

4. Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics for the questionnaire items were found as follows:

Table (3): Descriptive Statistics of Green Marketing Strategies Items

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Sig.
The company considers environmental laws and is committed to their application.	3.517	1.52053	0.0770	0.00
The management works on raising employees' awareness of environmental laws.	3.671	1.25429	0.0635	0.00
The company uses renewable energy sources	3.653	1.48884	0.0753	0.00

consistent with the environment.				
The company develops work systems and procedures aligned with environmental protection.	3.212	1.46013	0.0739	0.00
The company applies promotional policies encouraging the purchase of environmentally friendly products.	8		4	0
The company adopts promotional messages encouraging environmental preservation.	3.459	1.30733	0.0662	0.00
The company sets lower prices for green products compared to competitors in the market.	0		0	0
The company relies more on green pricing strategies based on green marketing principles.	3.379	1.15822	0.0586	0.00
	5		5	0
	3.366	1.41473	0.0716	0.00
	7		4	0
	3.394	1.25961	0.0637	0.00
	9		8	0

Source: SPSS v.25

According to the Likert scale, the average responses to the paragraphs on this axis indicate that the sample highly values green marketing strategies.

Table (4): Descriptive Statistics of Brand Image Items

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Sig.
The brand image of the organization generates a positive impression on	3.5128	1.51041	0.07648	0.000

customers when dealing with it.				
Customers feel confident when dealing with the organization.	3.5641	1.28657	0.06515	0.000
The brand image encourages customers to repeatedly purchase the organization's products.	3.3641	1.18289	0.05990	0.000
Customers feel loyalty toward the organization.	3.3974	1.41185	0.07149	0.000
Customers believe the company's products are worth the required price.	3.3410	1.28432	0.06503	0.000
Customers perceive the company's products as high quality.	3.4513	1.52492	0.07722	0.000
Customers believe that the company's products meet their needs accurately.	3.5718	1.26805	0.06421	0.000

Source: SPSS v.25

According to the Likert criterion, the average responses to the paragraphs on this axis suggest that the sample highly values the brand's mental image.

5. Testing Research Hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Green marketing strategies significantly impact the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq.

Table (5): Testing the First Hypothesis

R	R ²	Modified correction	error		
.943	.890	.890	.407		
Regression	sum of squares	df	average square	F	Sig
	518.818	1	518.818	3132.447	.000
Residuals	64.263	388	.166		
Total	583.082	389			

Source: SPSS v.25

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The following is evident:

- The correlation value is 0.943, which indicates a strong relationship between the two hypothetical variables.
- The corrected determinant value is 0.890, meaning green marketing strategies explain 89% of the difference in brand image in an oil products distribution company.
- Sig < 0.05, meaning green marketing strategies significantly impact brand image in an oil products distribution company in Iraq. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Figure (2): The relationship between the variables of the first hypothesis

Source: SPSS v.25

The results presented in Table 6 and Figure 2 are explained by the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of the petroleum products distribution company in Iraq. This marketing technique often highlights the environmental benefits of products, such as low carbon footprints, energy efficiency, and recyclability. These are what customers currently demand and what attracts them to the company's products.

Hypothesis 2 states that there are no significant differences in the average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of the petroleum products distribution company in Iraq based on years of practical experience among the research sample.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher conducted an ANOVA.

Table (6): Testing the second hypothesis

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.212	3	3.737	2.713	.045
Within Groups	531.656	386	1.377		
Total	542.868	389			

Source: SPSS v.25

We find that Sig < 0.05 = 0.045. Therefore, based on the variable of years of practical experience among the research sample, we reject the null hypothesis that there are no significant differences in the average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of the Iraqi Oil Products Distribution Company.

These results, presented in Table 6, can be explained by employees' awareness of the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of the Iraqi Oil Products Distribution Company as their years of practical experience increase. This is due to the importance of green marketing strategies, which help customers better understand oil products. These strategies also confirm that purchasing the same brand each time provides consistent characteristics that distinguish it from competitors and better meet customers' needs. The image of the Iraqi Oil Products Distribution Company is represented by the sum of individuals' impressions of the company's brand, which vary from person to person.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Results

1. Green marketing strategies impact the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq.
2. Significant differences exist in the average responses regarding the impact of green marketing strategies on the brand image of an oil products distribution company in Iraq depending on years of practical experience among the research sample.

The researcher explains these results by the employees' (the research sample) awareness of the impact of green marketing strategies on the mental image of the brand as their years of practical experience increase. Using any one of the green marketing strategies increases brand value and improves the brand's mental image among customers and the product audience. This is due to today's increased attention toward a more sustainable environment and the resulting increase in green customers who are greatly interested in protecting the environment, especially from emissions left by oil companies. Therefore, as interest in the green aspect of production, promotion, and marketing increases, the brand image of the organization changes and becomes more popular, interactive, and valuable.

Recommendations

1. The petroleum products distribution company should adopt modern communication methods and use the internet for cost-effective and environmentally friendly marketing strategies. This strategy eliminates the need for paper advertisements, brochures, flyers, and booklets to promote environmentally friendly products, services, and initiatives.
2. The company's management should develop operating systems and procedures compatible with environmental conservation. They should also adopt promotional policies that encourage purchasing green products and educate new employees about environmental laws.
3. Management should work to improve the company's image to motivate customers to make repeat purchases. They should feel that the products precisely meet their needs, are high quality, and are worth the price.

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